

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B484		
Date:	05 NOV 2009		
Take Off:	10:19:11Z	Z	Z
Landing:	11:48:18Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	1h 29m 7s	h m s	h m s

Campaign: QUEFA
Operating Area: London (M25) and Norwich

POB Position	Name	Institute
1 Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2 Co	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight
3 Pilot 3	Alan Foster	Directflight
4 CCM training	Robbie Voden	Directflight
5 Mission Scientist	Ruth Purvis	York/FAAM
6 Flight manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
7 Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM
8 CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
9 WAS	Shalini Punjabi	York University
10		
11		
12		
13		
14		
15		
16		
17		
18		
19		

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
Y	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
	Pre-flight log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
Y	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-11-05	Alan Woolley	Initial version
r1			
r2			

B484 08:24:15-11:59:35

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

QUEFA sorties

Back-to-back flights around London and then Norwich to quantify the emissions of Volatile organic compounds and other trace gases from these areas.

Each flight will involve two consecutive circuits around the city centres at fixed altitude within the boundary layer.

Missed approaches at nearby airports will give us a profile through the atmosphere and verify the position of the boundary layer. These will be performed at the start and end of each flight to check whether it has altered in this time.

WAS canisters should be filled in "fast-fill" mode. Given the relatively large number of WAS canisters on board we should aim to get an even spacing between samples (around one every 1 – 1.5 minutes) REGARDLESS of whether CO is calibrating.

CO calibrations should be performed twice during the circuits, but not over the same location to ensure data coverage.

Figure 1: Position of Waypoints during circuits around London and Norwich.

London sortie: F – A – B – C – D – E – F – A – B – C – D – E

Norwich sortie: G – H – I – J – K – L – G – H – I – J – K – L – G

Sortie 1: London (approximately 3 hours)

#	approx time	approx altitude	detail
(1)		take off	Take off and ascend to FL100
(2)		10,000 ft	transit to operating area - <i>Fill some WAS canisters (5) at this level.</i>
(3)		descend	Descend into Northolt airport and perform a missed approach
(4)		ascend	Ascend to 2300 ft. - <i>Or minimum safe altitude</i>
(5)		2300 ft	Perform two complete anti-clockwise circuits of the city at this level starting at point F (see figure 1). F – A – B – C – D – E – F – A – B – C – D – E. - <i>fill the remaining WAS canisters equally spread around both circuits approximately every 90 s.</i>
(6)		descend	Descend into Northolt airport and perform a missed approach
(7)		ascend	Ascend to above 2300 ft (likely to be 4500 ft) - <i>to verify the boundary layer height has not changed during the flight</i>
(8)		4500 ft	Transit to Cranfield
(9)		landing	Land at Cranfield

CO calibrations

1. before take off
2. during transit to operational area at 10,000 ft (#2)
3. start of circuits at 2300 ft (#6) around point A (see figure 1)
4. end of circuits at 2300 ft (#6) around point D (see figure 1)
5. during transit to Cranfield at 10,000 ft (#9)

Sortie 2: Norwich (approximately 2 hours)

#	approx time	approx altitude	detail
(1)		take off	Take off and ascend to FL100
(2)		10,000 ft	transit to operating area - <i>Fill some WAS canisters (5) at this level.</i>
(3)		descend	Descend into Norwich international airport and perform a missed approach
(4)		ascend	Ascend to 1300 ft. - <i>Or minimum safe altitude</i>
(5)		2300 ft	Perform two complete anti-clockwise circuits of the city at this level starting at point G (see figure 1). G - H - I - J - K - L - G - H - I - J - K - L - G. - <i>fill the remaining WAS canisters equally spread around both circuits approximately every 70 s.</i>
(6)		descend	Descend into Norwich international airport and perform a missed approach
(7)		ascend	Ascend to FL100 - <i>to verify the boundary layer height has not changed during the flight</i>
(8)		10,000 ft	Transit to Cranfield at FL100
(9)		landing	Land at Cranfield

CO calibrations

1. before take off
2. during transit to operational area at 10,000 ft (#2)
3. start of circuits at 1300 ft (#6) around point G (see figure 1)
4. end of circuits at 1300 ft (#6) around point K (see figure 1)
5. during transit to Cranfield at 10,000 ft (#9)

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B484

Date: 5/11/09

Project: QUEFA

Location: London M25

Start End

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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101318		taxy	0.93 kft	058	
101911		T/O	0.92 kft	212	from Cranfield
102626	103031	Run 1.1	8.0 - 7.8 kft	099	
103556	103955	Profile 1	3.6 - 0.73 kft	267	
104350	112515	Run 2.1	2.9 - 2.6 kft	233	
104441		abeam F	2.9 kft	272	
105005		at A	2.9 kft	234	
105202		run 2.1	2.8 kft	143	skip down
105801		at B	2.8 kft	139	
110227		Run 2.1	2.6 kft	089	skip down
110547		at C	2.5 kft	083	
111300		past D	2.2 kft	337	1 min ago
111815		at E	2.4 kft	258	
112538	112750	Profile 2	2.3 - 0.71 kft	257	
114818		Land	0.88 kft	214	cranfield

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B484

Date: 05 Nov 09

Instruments

1. Nevzorov cable found loose and fixed, but this hasn't fixed the Nevz tcw.
2. CIP25 imaging and total water not functioning, conc and size ok.
3. Intermittent satcom service (swift64)

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Flight:

B483

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom Phones:
 Satcom Data:
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (Canister):
 CDP (Fuselage):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI Inlet:
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 CIMS:
 QCL:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Flight:

B484

KEY

- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

- Duff Data
- Minor Problem
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- Buck CR2:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

- HORACE:
- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom Phones:
- Satcom Data:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- PCASP SPP-200:
- 2DS:
- ADA:
- CAPS:
- CCN:
- CDP (Canister):
- CDP (Fuselage):
- CIP 100 (PIP):
- CIP 25 (CIP):
- CPI:
- CVI Inlet:
- CVI PCASP-X:
- CVI Ly-A Hygro:
- FSSP (UMan):
- SID1:
- SID2:
- SID3:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- CPC 3786 H2O:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC (AMS):
- SMPS (AMS):
- CPC 3010A (CVI):
- INC:
- Mini-LIDAR:
- SP2:
- UHSAS:
- VACC:

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- CIMS:
- QCL:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOx FAAM:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR (big):
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Cloud Physics Flight Log B484

Date:	Operator:	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	AUX1 Time:	AUX2 Time:
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		CIP-15		SID2		FFSSP	
Operated?	N		Y		Y		Y		Y		Y	
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	N/A	Vref (>7V):	8.2	El#1 V (>1):	2.32	El#1 V (>1):	2.55	Comms?:	Y	Vref (>3V)	2.9
	Data TX?	N/A	Sample flow	1.16	El#32 V (>1):	2.95	El#32 V (>1):	3.37				
			Sheath flow	14.0	El#64 V (>1)	1.87	El#64 V (>1)	2.62				
			Spectra ok?	Y								

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y	

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
Pre flight												Due to issue with corrupt imaging on CIP greyscale swapped to old version of PADS software. No imaging on CIP-100 due to broken data acquisition card.
10:20												Heaters on
10:25												Found that the old version of PADS software had no CIP greyscale images but had perfect CIP-100 images. It seems that the cables to the 2 imaging data acquisition cards have been swapped. Returned to the newer software version and swapped cards in the settings.
10:35												CP software back running. No CIP greyscale images due to brocken imaging card. CIP 100 images seem fine. Will confirm swapped cables on ground if possible.
11:35												Pcasp heater off

CDP	Laser V:		
FFSSP	Ref V:		
SID 3	Laser V:		
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

asxx 05/11/2009 06:00 UTC

This is the WAS log for flight b484A on 05/11/2009

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:27:25 ,bottle, 57
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:28:27,Bottle,57
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:28:46 ,bottle, 58
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:29:46,Bottle,58
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:29:59 ,bottle, 59
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:31:00,Bottle,59
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:43:50 ,bottle, 60
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:44:20,Bottle,60
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:44:54 ,bottle, 61
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:45:24,Bottle,61
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:46:31 ,bottle, 62
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:47:01,Bottle,62
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:47:58 ,bottle, 63
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:48:28,Bottle,63
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:49:37 ,bottle, 64
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:50:08,Bottle,64
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:50:30 ,bottle, 49
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:51:00,Bottle,49
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:52:11 ,bottle, 50
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:52:41,Bottle,50
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:53:49 ,bottle, 51
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:53:57 ,bottle, 53
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:54:18,Bottle,53
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:54:40 ,bottle, 52
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:55:11,Bottle,52
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:55:24 ,bottle, 51
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:55:54,Bottle,51
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:56:29 ,bottle, 54
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:56:59,Bottle,54
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:57:38 ,bottle, 55
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:58:08,Bottle,55
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:58:19 ,bottle, 56
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:58:49,Bottle,56
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,10:59:33 ,bottle, 25
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:00:04,Bottle,25
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:01:13 ,bottle, 26
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:01:43,Bottle,26
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:02:48 ,bottle, 27
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:03:19,Bottle,27
Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:04:35 ,bottle, 28
End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:05:05,Bottle,28

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:05:56 ,bottle, 29

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:06:26,Bottle,29

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:07:17 ,bottle, 30

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:07:47,Bottle,30

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:08:34 ,bottle, 31

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:09:04,Bottle,31

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:10:20 ,bottle, 32

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:10:51,Bottle,32

This is the WAS log for flight b484A on 05/11/2009

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:14:57 ,bottle, 41

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:15:28,Bottle,41

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:16:23 ,bottle, 42

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:16:53,Bottle,42

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:17:29 ,bottle, 43

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:17:59,Bottle,43

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:18:57 ,bottle, 44

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:19:27,Bottle,44

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:19:38 ,bottle, 45

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:20:08,Bottle,45

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:20:29 ,bottle, 46

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:20:59,Bottle,46

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:21:07 ,bottle, 47

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:21:38,Bottle,47

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:21:43 ,bottle, 48

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:22:13,Bottle,48

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:22:24 ,bottle, 16

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:22:54,Bottle,16

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:23:03 ,bottle, 17

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:23:33,Bottle,17

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:23:42 ,bottle, 18

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:24:12,Bottle,18

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:24:24 ,bottle, 19

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:24:55,Bottle,19

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:25:07 ,bottle, 20

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:25:37,Bottle,20

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:25:44 ,bottle, 21

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:26:14,Bottle,21

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:27:01 ,bottle, 22

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:27:32,Bottle,22

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:27:40 ,bottle, 23

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:28:10,Bottle,23

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:28:16 ,bottle, 24

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:28:46,Bottle,24

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:28:55 ,bottle, 1

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:29:26,Bottle,1

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:29:33 ,bottle, 2

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:30:03,Bottle,2

Start FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:30:12 ,bottle, 3

End FillTime, 05/11/2009,11:30:42,Bottle,3